

Impact Factor: 5.19

ISSN: 2181-0664

DOI: 10.26739/2181-0664

www.tadqiqot.uz

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

Volume 4, Issue 5

2023

ISSN 2181-0664

Doi Journal 10.26739/2181-0664

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

4 ЖИЛД, 5 СОН

УЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ

ТОМ 4, НОМЕР 5

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

VOLUME 4, ISSUE 5

ТОШКЕНТ-2023

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ | UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

№5 (2023) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-0664-2023-5>

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THE FREQUENCY OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF MULTIPLE PRIMARY MALIGNANT TUMORS OF THE FEMALE REPRODUCTIVE SYSTEM

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8402771>

ABSTRACT

The study aimed to investigate the frequency of the development of synchronous and metachronous tumors and the combination of different types of cancer among patients with primary-multiple malignant tumors of the female reproductive system. This is relevant for improving the diagnosis of this category of patients. 80 patients with multiple primary malignant tumors with lesions of the female reproductive system (II-III clinical stages of the disease) were included in the study. This research found that 27.5% of patients had synchronous tumors and 72.5% had metachronous tumors. Among the 38 patients with breast cancer, 23.7% had synchronous cancer of the second breast, and 7.9% had ovarian cancer. Synchronous breast cancer was detected in 22.7% of patients with primary ovarian cancer, 25.0% with uterine body cancer, and 25.0% with cervical cancer. Metachronous tumors were diagnosed in 68.4% of patients with breast cancer, 77.3% with ovarian cancer, 75.0% with uterine body cancer, and 75.0% with cervical cancer. The most common time for metachronous tumors to be detected was between 6 months and 1 year and between 1 year and 2 years in 44.8% of patients. Thus, each female reproductive system tumor should be considered an indicator of other oncopathological risks. And effective dispensary monitoring will allow for monitoring the development of multiple primary malignant tumors in this type of patient in advance.

Keywords: metachronous tumors; primary multiple malignant tumors; tumors of the female reproductive system; synchronous tumors.

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ЧАСТОТА РАЗВИТИЯ ПЕРВИЧНО-МНОЖЕСТВЕННЫХ ЗЛОКАЧЕСТВЕННЫХ ОПУХОЛЕЙ ЖЕНСКОЙ РЕПРОДУКТИВНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Цель исследования - изучить частоту развития синхронных и метасинхронных опухолей, а также сочетания различных видов рака среди больных первично-множественными злокачественными опухолями женской репродуктивной системы. Это актуально для улучшения диагностики данной категории пациентов. В исследование включены 80 больных с первично-множественными злокачественными опухолями с поражением женской репродуктивной системы (II-III клинические стадии заболевания). В ходе данного исследования установлено, что у 27,5% больных наблюдались синхронные опухоли, а у 72,5% — метасинхронные. Среди 38 больных раком молочной железы у 23,7% был синхронный рак второй молочной железы, у 7,9% — рак яичников. Синхронный рак молочной железы выявлен у 22,7% больных первичным раком яичников, у 25,0% больных раком тела матки и у 25,0% больных раком шейки матки. Метасинхронные опухоли диагностированы у 68,4% больных раком молочной железы, 77,3% - раком яичников, 75,0% - раком тела матки, 75,0% - раком шейки матки. Чаще всего метасинхронные опухоли выявлялись в возрасте от 6 месяцев до 1 года и от 1 года до 2 лет у 44,8% пациентов. Таким образом, каждую опухоль женской репродуктивной системы следует рассматривать как индикатор риска развития других онкопатологий. А эффективный диспансерный контроль позволит заблаговременно отслеживать развитие первично-множественных злокачественных опухолей у данного типа больных.

Ключевые слова: метасинхронные опухоли; первично-множественные злокачественные опухоли; опухоли женской репродуктивной системы; синхронные опухоли.

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Respublika ixtisoslashtirilgan onkologiya va radiologiya
ilmiy-amaliy tibbiyot markazi Toshkent, O'zbekiston

AYOLLAR REPRODUKTIV TIZIMINING BIRINCHI KO'P XARXATLI O'SMALARINI RIVOJLANISH CHASTOSLIGI

ANNOTATSIYA

Tadqiqotning maqsadi – ayol jinsiy tizimining birlamchi ko'p xavfli o'smalari bo'lgan bemorlarda sinxron va metaxron o'smalarning rivojlanish chastotasini, shuningdek turli xil saraton turlarining kombinatsiyasini o'rganishdir. Bu ushbu toifadagi bemorlarning tashxisini yaxshilash uchun dolzarbdir. Tadqiqotga ayollarning reproduktiv tizimiga ta'sir qiluvchi birlamchi ko'p xavfli o'smalari bo'lgan 80 bemor (kasallikning II-III klinik bosqichlari) ishtirok etdi. Ushbu tadqiqot bemorlarning 27,5 foizida sinxron, 72,5 foizida metaxron o'smalari borligi aniqlandi. Ko'krak bezi saratoni bilan og'rigan 38 bemorning 23,7 foizida ikkinchi ko'krakning sinxron saratoni, 7,9 foizida tuxumdon saratoni bor edi. Sinxron ko'krak saratoni birlamchi tuxumdon saratoni bilan og'rigan bemorlarning 22,7 foizida, bachadon saratoni bilan og'rigan bemorlarning 25,0 foizida va bachadon bo'yni saratoni bilan og'rigan bemorlarning 25,0 foizida aniqlangan. Ko'krak bezi saratoni bilan og'rigan bemorlarning 68,4 foizida, tuxumdon saratoni 77,3 foizida, bachadon saratoni 75,0 foizida, bachadon bo'yni saratoni bilan og'rigan bemorlarning 75,0 foizida metaxron o'smalari aniqlangan. Ko'pincha metaxron o'smalar bemorlarning 44,8 foizida 6 oydan 1 yoshgacha va 1 yoshdan 2 yoshgacha bo'lgan davrda aniqlangan. Shunday qilib, ayol jinsiy tizimining har bir shishi boshqa saraton patologiyalarini rivojlanish xavfining ko'rsatkichi sifatida ko'rib chiqilishi kerak. Va samarali klinik monitoring ushbu turdagi bemorlarda bir nechta asosiy malign o'smalarning rivojlanishini erta kuzatish imkonini beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: metaxron o'smalar; birlamchi ko'p malign o'smalar; ayol jinsiy tizimining o'smalari; sinxron o'smalar.

Introduction. There is an increasing interest in studying issues related to the problem of multiple primary malignant tumors (MPMT) among oncologists due to the widespread increase in the number of patients with this type of oncopathology [2,19]. Many researchers agree that

polyineoplasias are most often found in women. It is associated with an increase in the incidence of the reproductive system hormone-dependent tumors, which is functionally represented by the mammary glands, uterus and ovaries [14,18,22,23]. Malignant tumors of the reproductive system are the most frequent in the structure of cancer morbidity in women and their total share exceeds 35%. According to various authors, the frequency of MPMT of the female reproductive system ranges from 0.8% to 12.6% of all cancer cases of these localities [1,6,11].

The time boundary between the synchronicity and metachronism of malignant tumor development has been a long-standing issue. Currently, most authors consider the most reliable interval for the occurrence of the second metachronous tumor to be a period of more than 6 months from the diagnosis of the first one, although this is rather conditional. In the vast majority of cases (75-80%), metachronous tumors occur in the period from 3 to 15 years, although isolated cases of the second tumor's occurrence at a later time are described [7,20,21].

According to various authors data in patients with breast cancer (BC) MPMT occurs in 1.9-7.1% of cases. Most often, breast cancer is associated with malignant tumors of the female reproductive system (33-42%): ovarian cancer (OC) (15-17%), uterine body cancer (UBC) (12-14%), cervical cancer (CC) (10-12%). Next in the frequency of occurrence is cancer of the colon and rectum (12-13%), then the stomach (14-15%) and thyroid cancer (7.7%). The remaining localizations of malignant tumors are described in single observations [2,3,24].

Among UBC patients, the most frequent combination is noted with breast tumors, which confirms the hormonal dependence of malignant cervical tumors. In UBC patients, the relative risk of breast cancer (BC) is 13.6% in the first year, 5.3% in the fifth, 3.9% in the tenth and 3.0% in the fifteenth year. In patients with breast cancer, the relative risk of UBC is 9.0% in the first year, 2.4% in the fifth, 2.2% in the tenth, and 3.6% in the fifteenth year. Consequently, in patients with both BC and UBC, the risk of a second tumor developing is realized mainly in the first year due to synchronous polyineoplasias. The synchronicity of UBC and OC development and the relatively short interval between the development of UBC and BC, indirectly indicate the common pathogenetic mechanisms of these malignant tumors' development [16,17,25].

The study aimed to investigate the frequency of the development of synchronous and metachronous tumors, as well as the combination of different types of cancer among patients with primary-multiple malignant tumors of the female reproductive system. This is relevant for improving the diagnosis of this category of patients.

Material and methods. The study included 80 patients with multiple primary malignant tumors with lesions of the female reproductive system, who were examined and treated in the departments of oncomammology, oncogynecology, and chemotherapy-2 of Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Oncology and Radiology from 2015 to 2021. The patients were divided into four groups based on the type of cancer: breast cancer, ovarian cancer, uterine body cancer, and cervical cancer. The age of the patients varied depending on the type of cancer. Disease-specific staging was performed according to the International Clinical Classification TNM (7th ed. and 8th ed.) and FIGO (2009 and 2016). The study found that the most common stages of the disease varied depending on the type of cancer. In breast cancer patients, IIB and IIA stages of the disease were more common. In patients with ovarian cancer, IIB, IIA, and IIIC stages were more common. In uterine body cancer patients, IIB and IIC stages were more common, and in cervical cancer patients, IIB and IIIB stages were more common.

Results and discussion. The study found that infiltrating ductal cancer was the most common type among patients with breast cancer, accounting for 57.9% of cases. A mixed form of ductal and lobular types of cancer was found in 23.7% of cases, while infiltrating cancer occurred in 7.9% of patients. The study also examined the morphological structure of ovarian cancer and found that serous cystadenocarcinoma was the most common type, accounting for 45.5% of cases. Undifferentiated cancer was found in 27.3% of cases, endometrioid cancer in 18.2% of cases, and mucinous cystadenocarcinoma in 9.1% of cases.

Histological analysis of UBC biopsy samples showed that in 8 (66.7%) patients endometrioid carcinoma was detected, in 2 (16.7%) cases – serous-papillary adenocarcinoma, in 1 (8.3%) patient

– mixed carcinoma and 1 (8.3%) patient – light cell carcinoma. The morphological structure of the CC was also studied. Histologically, 4 (50.0%) patients had squamous cell carcinoma with keratinization, 3 (37.5%) – without keratinization. Adenocarcinoma was detected in 1 (12.5%) patient.

When analyzing the family oncological history of the examined patients, the following was noted:

- 22 (57.9%) blood relatives on the maternal line had breast cancer.
- 2 (5.3%) of them had ovarian cancer.
- 4 (10.6%) had a combination of ovarian and breast cancer.

The study of the anamnesis data showed that in most of the patients – 35 (43.8%) - the disease symptoms appeared from 3 to 6 months.

In our research, synchronous tumors were found in 22 patients (27.5%), while metachronous tumors were found in 58 patients (72.5%) out of the surveyed individuals. Synchronous tumors, appeared in a period from 3 to 6 months, were found in 12 (31.6%) patients with breast cancer, synchronous second breast cancer was found in 9 (23.7%) of them, and ovarian cancer – in 3 (7.9%) cases. In patients with primary detected OC, UBC, and CC, synchronous breast cancer was simultaneously detected in 5 (22.7%), 3 (25.0%) and in 2 (25.0%) patients, respectively (Tab. 1).

Table 1

Distribution of examined patients with synchronous tumors, n=80

Primary detected tumor	Synchronous tumor	Patients' quantity	
		absolute	%
Breast cancer (BC), n=38	BC	9	23.7
	OC	3	7.9
Ovarian cancer (OC), n=22	BC	5	22.7
Uterine body cancer (UBC), n=12	BC	3	25.0
Cervical cancer (CC), n=8	BC	2	25.0

Metachronous cancer in terms of 6 months and above was detected in a larger number of patients. Thus, metachronous tumors were subsequently detected in 26 (68.4%) patients with breast cancer, among them metachronous second breast cancer – in 14 (36.8%), UBC – in 7 (18.4%) and OC – in 5 (13.2%) patients. Metachronous breast cancer was detected in 17 (77.3%) and 6 (75.0%) patients with OC and CC, respectively. And in UBC patients, metachronous breast cancer was detected in 7 (58.3%) examined patients and OC – in 2 (16.7%) cases (Tab. 2).

Table 2

Distribution of examined patients with metachronous tumors, n=80

Primary detected tumor	Metachronous tumor	Patients quantity	
		absolute	%
Breast cancer (BC), n=38	BC	14	36.8
	UBC	7	18.4
	OC	5	13.2
Ovarian cancer (OC), n=22	BC	17	77.3
Uterine body cancer (UBC), n=12	BC	7	58.3
	OC	2	16.7
Cervical cancer (CC), n=8	BC	6	75.0

According to Figure 1, a greater variety of combinations of metachronous malignant tumors of the female reproductive system is observed when the primary tumor is breast cancer. In most cases, the metachronous tumor arises in the remaining breast. In the case of primary ovarian cancer and cervical cancer, metachronous tumors were only observed in the breast.

Figure 1. Percentage of metachronous combined tumors in patients with primary multiple malignant tumors, n=80.

The timing of metachronous tumors occurrence in patients is shown in Figure 2, from which it follows that the most often tumors were detected in the period from 6 months to 1 year and from 1 year to 2 years in 26 (44.8%) patients.

Figure 2. Distribution of metachronous tumors in the examined patients at different observation periods, in percentages.

Thus, MPMT represent a significant issue in modern oncology. Most of these polyineoplasias occur in women and are usually manifested at the development of hormone-dependent tumors of the reproductive system and are most often associated with breast cancer. In this regard, each of the tumors of the female reproductive system should be considered as the risk indicator of other oncopathologies. Effective dispensary monitoring will allow to monitor the development of MPMT in this type of patient in advance.

Conclusion. Our research found synchronous tumors in 22 (27.5%) out of 80 patients with primary-multiple tumors. In our studies synchronous tumors were found in 12 (31.6%) patients with

breast cancer, synchronous second breast cancer was found in 9 (23.7%) of them and ovarian cancer – in 3 (7.9%) cases. In patients with primary detection of OC, UBC, and CC, synchronous breast cancer was simultaneously detected in 5 (22,7%), in 3 (25,0%) and in 2 (25.0%) patients, respectively.

Metachronous tumors occurred in 58 (72.5%) of 80 examined patients. Metachronous tumors at the period of 6 months and above were subsequently detected in 26 (68.4%) patients with breast cancer: metachronous second breast cancer – in 14 (36.8%), UBC – in 7 (18.4%) and OC – in 5 (13.2%) patients. Metachronous breast cancer was detected in patients with OC and CC (17 (77.3%) and 6 (75.0%), respectively). In patients with UBC we found metachronous breast cancer and ovarian cancer (7 (58.3%) and 2 (16.7%), respectively).

Metachronous tumors were most often detected from 6 months to 1 year and from 1 year to 2 years in 26 (44.8%) patients.

Primary-multiple malignant tumors in female oncology are primarily associated with breast cancer. Uterine body cancer is also associated with ovarian cancer, which is observed in synchronous and metachronous forms of their development. In the case of primary ovarian cancer and cervical cancer, metachronous tumors were observed only in the breast.

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UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

VOLUME 4, ISSUE 5

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